

ORGANIZATION OF MARKETING ACTIVITIES OF SMALL BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURIAL SUBJECTS

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Abstract. The article provides brief information about the organization of marketing and management activities in small businesses and private enterprises and the work that should be done in this regard.

Key words: innovative marketing, concept, holding, corporation, image.

INTRODUCTION

In his address to the Oliy Majlis, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, said, "By an active entrepreneur, we mean business people who are able to produce competitive products, and most importantly, create new jobs and support not only themselves and their families, but also benefit the entire society. Our first task is to expand the ranks of such entrepreneurs, including bringing and introducing high-tech, technology and equipment based on the latest achievements of science to our country. If necessary, we should provide them with every opportunity to gain experience and mutually beneficial cooperation in leading foreign companies and organizations," they said. The 29th goal of the "New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" is to create conditions for the organization of business activities and the formation of permanent sources of income, to increase the share of the private sector in the GDP to 80% and the share of exports to 60% . It is important to organize marketing activities in small businesses and entrepreneurial entities in the formation and development of active entrepreneurship.

Today, the concept of marketing has become a philosophy of business, and it allows today's companies to anticipate consumer needs and meet consumer needs. The use of marketing technologies is not only the organization and management of work in the company, but also a creative approach to management processes.

In the conditions of increasing competition in the market, the success of small business entities is determined by the effectiveness of their marketing activities and marketing programs. Knowing and implementing the necessary tools of marketing today will help companies succeed in the market. It will be difficult to develop the economy without a deep study of the specific features of marketing

activities in small business in connection with the elements of the market mechanism, its principles and functions.

Marketing is an important basis of small business management, because its goal is to identify consumer needs and mobilize the resources of a small business in order to satisfy these needs. The development of the marketing concept is becoming more important in order to intensify the competition in the economy. Due to the effective use of marketing work in the field of commerce, this term was formed as a concept of managing an enterprise in competitive conditions .

Each small business operates in its own conditions and solves its own specific issues, and based on this, the marketing system will look different depending on where it is used and in which industry. This is one of the reasons why marketers should take into account the specific characteristics of economic sectors in the process of coordinating resource opportunities and consumer demand in the market environment.

A serious obstacle to the use of marketing technologies in small businesses is explained by the limited financial resources of such enterprises. Large production associations (holdings, corporations) have the opportunity to engage in marketing research, at least as an experiment, knowing that there is a risk of damage. They do this without rejecting traditional technologies. A small business hardly dares to spend huge amounts of money on marketing. However, marketing technologies such as market research and direct (without intermediaries) sales do not always require large funds, and in most cases such marketing activities are carried out by the enterprise with its own internal resources. can also do. It is also known that the direct damage caused by neglecting the marketing work in many cases exceeds the "saved" funds .

Based on the principles and forms of marketing service organization, in order to organize marketing services in small business entities, in all of them such work is performed not by individual full-time employees, but by the head of the enterprise or his deputy. Along with marketing work, they perform several tasks (accountant, manager, technologist, supplier, etc.). Although most of these leaders have higher, secondary and special education, they are engineers and technologists by specialty. Some of you don't even understand the meaning of the word "marketing". Most of the small enterprises have up to 25 workers and employees, about 90% of them are direct participants in production, and the rest are indirectly involved in this process. If the number of personnel is insufficient, the head of the enterprise will have to directly participate in economic operations. The main part of them are enterprises that have not been

established for a long time and are just establishing business. Most of the employees have interchangeable qualifications and experience, the division of labor and specialization has not deepened, and the leader is responsible for solving issues at different levels. Determining the amount of production, supply, management, customer attraction and sales are also among the main tasks of the head of the enterprise.

The process of increasing the number of employees and expanding the activities of the enterprise leads to a deepening of the division of labor, in turn, each employee or worker has a function that he performs separately. The same process is observed in enterprises with 25 or more employees. In them, management of the production process, accounting, supply, and sales are assigned to individual persons, and the manager establishes general control. However, companies do not have a marketing staff or department. Therefore, the organization of marketing services, based on the principles and forms presented in the literature, cannot be directly applied to enterprises. Therefore, it is a natural necessity to propose a unique principle of marketing organization in relation to enterprises. In addition, it is impossible to apply project (vertical) or matrix organizational forms of marketing to enterprises. Because such forms require several marketing experts, more material and financial resources. Enterprises do not have such opportunities. Therefore, it is necessary to develop an organizational form of marketing specific to them. Taking into account the characteristics of the network, it is necessary to develop the organizational principle and form of marketing services and create a new model.

Proposed model: understaffing of KBS; small volume of production; made taking into account the mode of working hours of managers and employees, etc. That is, in KBS, it is assumed that the employee needs to perform several functions, the production operation in the enterprise is low, and as a result, the manager can find time to deal with other functions. Based on this, the model shows that the manager or his deputy performs other functions in parallel with marketing. The difference from the listed principles is that marketing is attached as a function based on the free time and ability of KBS employees to perform marketing work. No jobs will be created and no workers will be hired to fulfill this responsibility. Marketing decisions are closely related to the effectiveness of business activities. A mistake in decision-making can have serious consequences. This means not only the risk of bankruptcy, but also the loss of financial resources and, at the same time, the loss of image. In the conditions of increasing competition in the market, the success of a small enterprise is determined by the effectiveness of its

marketing activities and marketing programs. Knowing and implementing today's essential marketing tools can give businesses a competitive advantage and help them succeed in the marketplace.

CONCLUSION

In short, a necessary condition for the operation and development of small enterprises in the conditions of the innovative economy is the development and implementation of a marketing strategy based on the use of marketing technologies.

Marketing work (research, planning, implementation of tactical and strategic plans, sales organization, analysis, control, etc.) is carried out in parallel by one employee without being subordinate to others, means "horizontal" form.

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